

**TRADITIONAL AND NON-TRADITIONAL WAYS OF STUDYING
FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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Abstract: The goals and motives of learning a foreign language in this world acquire specific goals. All traditional methods of teaching a foreign language work successfully, but it is extremely necessary to use modern educational tools, especially for independent work of students. Close cooperation of teachers, psychologists, programmers will lead to the creation of effective teaching methods that will meet the requirements of modern society.

Keywords: methods, methods, advantages and disadvantages.

The method or method of teaching is "a system of purposeful actions of the teacher, organizing the cognitive and practical activities of the student, ensuring the assimilation of the content of education and thereby achieving the learning goals."

Throughout the history of mankind, a great many different educational methods have been developed. At first, all methods of teaching foreign languages were borrowed from programs designed to teach the so-called "dead languages" - Latin and Greek, in which almost the entire educational process was reduced to reading and translation.

It is generally believed that there are traditional and non-traditional ways of learning a foreign language. Under the traditional way of learning a foreign language, it is customary to understand the grammar-translation method of learning and all educated from it.

Grammar-translation method. This method, the foundations of which were laid by the enlighteners at the end of the XVIII century, took shape by the middle of the XX-th under the name "Grammar-translational method". According to this method, proficiency in language is proficiency in grammar and vocabulary. The process of improvement is understood as a movement from one grammatical scheme to another. The main purpose of this method was perfectly characterized by the great linguist V. Humboldt: "The purpose of teaching a language is to communicate knowledge about its general structure."

Many teachers still rely on it in their work, because the grammar-translation method remains the basic method of training specialists in language universities in our country. Thus, the basis of the course is the grammatical topics on which the relevant texts are selected. During classes, a lot of exercises are used to form grammatical constructions, for example, you need to replace the active form with a passive one, change the tenses in a phrase, change the structure using a certain grammatical phenomenon, etc.

Today, the lexico-grammatical methodology develops four basic language skills: speaking, reading, listening and writing. Considerable attention is paid to the analysis of foreign texts, as well as the writing of essays and expositions. In the mid-50s, it became obvious that this method did not meet the requirements of linguistics that had been formed by that time, the result was the emergence of a huge number of different techniques. I would like to tell you about some of them.

The method of silence. According to the method called "Silent way", which appeared in the mid-60s, the principle of teaching a foreign language is as follows. Knowledge of the language is initially inherent in the person who wants to study it, and the most important thing is not to interfere with the student and not to impose the point of view of the teacher. Following this method, the teacher initially says nothing. Teaching pronunciation at junior levels, he uses complex color tables on which each color or symbol denotes a certain sound, and so presents new words. For

example, to "say" the word "table", you first need to show a square indicating the sound "t", then a square indicating the sound "hey" and so on.

The communicative method. The 70s were marked by the appearance of the so-called communicative method, the main purpose of which is to teach a person to communicate, to make his speech understandable to the interlocutor. The most effective method for memorizing words and suppressing the language barrier comes to replace the boring study of languages from a textbook - a communicative one. In fact, this technique did not even have to be invented - initially, the exchange of knowledge with a neighboring tribe took place at the level of live contact, nonverbal communication, gestures and facial expressions. Learning a language by contacting a native speaker is much easier and faster. In the learning process, it makes sense to split into groups or work in pairs, regardless of the level of knowledge and vocabulary.

With the advent of modern means of communication, the task has become doubly simplified - wherever you are, you can always find a friend from the other side of the planet and practice learning the language by talking on Skype. This is the second, after the traditional, most popular method of learning foreign languages. The essence of this method is not to memorize the rules and techniques of reading and composing dry sentences, but to interact with people using their knowledge. A properly constructed program gives fast and effective results, so the popularity of this method is not surprising.

Lexico-translational or analytical method. The method was used in different European countries (England, France, Switzerland). The focus of this method was vocabulary. The vocabulary was created by memorizing original works by heart. A literal line-by-line translation was used. Grammar was relegated to the background and studied haphazardly as a commentary on the text. The lexical-translation method pursued mainly general educational goals and ensured the development of reading

and translation skills. The representatives of the lexical-translation method are Chauvann (Switzerland), Jacoto (France) and Hamilton (England).

The lexical-translation method was more progressive in comparison with the grammatical-translation method due to the use of literary texts reflecting the norm of the studied language and the absence of scholastic grammar study.

The next popular method that appeared in the second half of the 19th century is the natural method. The main idea of the natural method is that when teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to artificially create a language environment similar to the one that surrounds a child when mastering his native speech. Hence the name of the method: natural or natural. The most prominent representatives of this method were M. Berlitz, F. Guen, M. Walter, etc. The main attention in the methodology was paid to the teaching of oral speech: it was assumed that the possession of oral speech provides the ability to read and write, which only requires mastering the technique of reading and writing.

The main purpose of teaching with the natural method is to teach students to speak a foreign language. The proponents of this method proceeded from the premise that, having learned to speak, students will be able to read and write in the language being studied, even without being taught the technique of reading and writing. They developed, mainly, the methodology of the initial stage and taught students mainly everyday language, pursuing exclusively practical goals.

On its basis, in the late XIX – early XX centuries, a direct method of teaching emerged, in the development of which psychologists and linguists (V. Fietor, O. Espersen), as well as methodologists (Sh. Schweitzer, G. Wendt, E. Simoneau, etc.). The purpose of this technique was to teach practical language proficiency, mainly in its oral form. The main difference from the natural method is the appeal to a live spoken language and the creation of a methodology for teaching oral speech.

The natural method, on the contrary, relied on literary texts as a role model and simply took ready-made communicative units of oral speech. Also, the direct

method allowed the use of reading and writing, contributing to the consolidation of new material, which was not provided for in the natural method.

Stickers with names. The method is ideal for memorizing nouns used by us in everyday life. Write on the sticker "refrigerator" and glue it on the refrigerator, "door" will take place on the door, and the inscription "table" will decorate the kitchen table. Thus, day after day, seeing the "signed" objects around, the student automatically learns foreign names. In the process of learning, the leaves can be changed, supplemented and increased in number. The method is good for working at the initial stages, but later you will still have to resort to communicative practices and the study of basic grammatical rules.

Audio and video linguistic method. In the 1970s, on the basis of the above-mentioned methods, an audio-linguistic method emerged, which provoked the emergence of language courses and language classes.

Proponents of the audio-lingual method believed that it was necessary to memorize grammatical and phraseological structures of the language by repeatedly repeating them in ready-made educational dialogues, which would allow them to be used automatically at the right moment. The essence of the method was that the student listens and repeats phrases for a long time after the teacher or the phonogram, and only starting from the second level, he is allowed to start saying one or two phrases from himself, continuing to repeat the rest.

The video method, by analogy, consists in watching movies or videos in an unknown language. Subtitles for videos and translation of audio recordings will help to simplify the task and speed up learning. An example is the WHILE WATCHING TV method. The method is also good for vocabulary replenishment and immersion in a foreign language, but without communication you are unlikely to be able to overcome the barrier and feel quite relaxed in communication.

The method will help to form a clear pronunciation and learn how to build sentences. The grammar was mastered on the basis of structures identified in

accordance with the ideas of structural linguistics. This method is suitable for those with well-developed hearing.

Edutainment. The word "edutainment" comes from two English words "education" - "education" and "entertainment" - "entertainment". While learning (not only a foreign language), various "entertaining" techniques have been used for a long time: watching movies during classes, interactive tours in galleries and museums, educational and entertaining videos, even various computer games. Anything, in one way or another connected with non-boring training. If you feel that you have lost all motivation, you are incredibly bored and you are one step away from quitting everything halfway, then this method is for you. In addition, it is said that through various "entertainments" the student establishes a special emotional connection with the subject being studied.

Emotional drawing. This method is based on the concept of emotional memory. Thanks to her, as many scientists believe, a person remembers most of the information. So, take an album sheet and draw a picture on it with colored pencils or markers. Next to the picture, write in English what it depicts. At the same time, your creative abilities do not play any role.

It is important to concentrate on the name of the subject that you are drawing. This method is very often used when teaching English to young children. Kids like to draw, and the paintings they create often decorate their rooms. So this is another plus to memorizing words.

In addition to the methods described above, there are many more author's different methods and ways of learning a foreign language.

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